

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

O. X. Ashiraliyeva

**THE BENEFITS OF OLIVE OIL FOR HUMAN HEALTH AND ITS
USE IN COSMETOLOGY**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/FEVRAL

